

Sodium Isopropyl Xanthate as a Substoichiometric Reagent for the Estimation of Silver

K. V. MURALIKRISHNA, B. POLAIAH and B. RANGAMANNAR*

Radiochemical Laboratories, Department of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati-517 502

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Xanthates are considered as important group of reagents in analytical chemistry. Among these group, ethyl xanthate has been studied extensively¹. It is generally felt that the other xanthates could be superior to ethyl xanthate. It is observed that increase in the alkyl chainlength increases the chemical reactivity of alkyl xanthates². Ni^{II} strongly reacts with the xanthates of methyl, ethyl, propyl, butyl and benzyl to form insoluble brownish yellow coloured complexes extractable into chloroform. However, all the complexes are similar as evidenced by spectral studies. It is fascinating to note that the above cited xanthate complexes of Ni^{II} have a uniform value of around 3.0 as the distribution constants. However, the formation constant and molar absorptivity at a wavelength of 420 nm show considerable variation from complex to complex. However, the propyl xanthate complex display the maximum stability³ ($\log \beta_n = 8.06$). Kovacs *et al.*⁴ studied polarographically the complexation properties for C₁-C₆ xanthates with Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II}. The thermodynamic parameters ΔH , ΔG , ΔS_{298} and $\log \beta_n$ were calculated. The values were observed to be nearly independent of the xanthate used. The overall formation constant decreased in the order, Zn < Cd < Hg. This observed order reflects the soft acid characteristics on the central atom which determines the strength of the metal-S bond. Effect of chain-length on the reactivity of xanthates is also evident from the work of Kolchmanova and Pikkat⁵. The use of combination of xanthate with hydrocarbon chains of different lengths increased lead and zinc extraction compared with the use of individual xanthates. Further, mixtures containing isopropyl xanthate gave the highest lead extraction.

Both the preparation and purification of sodium isopropyl xanthate have been described earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

Maximum and quantitative extraction of silver : isopropyl xanthate complex into nitrobenzene was observed from a 4.0 M nitric acid medium. Under substoichiometric conditions stipulated for reproducible substoichiometric isolation are rigorously achieved as indicated from the plateau portion of the radiometric titration curve. The equivalence point indicates the formation of a 1 : 1 complex. The calibration curve was found to be linear in the range of study, that is 4–12 μg and the extrapolated portion indicated the amount of tracer silver as 4 μg .

7 μg of each Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Tl^I, Tl^{III}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Al^{III}, Sb^{III}, Sr^{III}, Cr^{III}, Hg^{II}, Rb^I, Mn^{II}, Se^{IV}, citrate, EDTA, phosphate and cyanide did not interfere with extraction of 4 μg silver. Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} can be masked with cyanide. The representative determination with test solution indicates that silver can be determined by the present method with an average error of 2.02 % in the range 3–10 μg Ag.

The silver content of the sample film washing solution determined by the present method (Table 1) compared with the values obtained by the standard method⁷.

Experimental

Silver stock solution (1 mg/l ml) was prepared and standardised⁸ by dissolving AgNO₃ (0.157 g;

AnalaR) in double-distilled water (100 ml).

^{110m}Ag ($T_{1/2} = 253\text{d}$) was supplied by the Board of Radiation and Isotope Technology, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. Silver active solution was prepared by adding tracer solution (20 μl) to stock silver solution (1 ml) and made up to give a solution of 0.01 mg of Ag/ml. A $0.93 \times 10^{-4} M$ sodium isopropyl xanthate solution was prepared in double-distilled methanol.

TABLE-1

(a) Determination of Silver in Test Solution

Amount of Ag (mg)	
Taken	Found
3.03	2.93
4.04	4.16
5.05	5.01
7.07	6.91
9.09	8.84
10.10	10.04
Synthetic mixture :	
4 μg Ag^{I} + 2 μg each Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} , +10 mg CN^-	3.98
Average error :	2.02%

(b) Determination of Silver in Samples :

Sample	Amount of Ag determined (mg ml^{-1})	
	Present method	Standard method*
Black and white film washings	$3.31 + 0.12^a$	3.303 1
Colour film washings	$3.43 + 0.20^a$	3.434 4

* Ref. 7. ^aAverage of four determinations.

Each of the photofilm washings (1 ml) (collected locally) was treated with a few drops of nitric acid and diluted. The solution was filtered and made upto 25 ml.

The activity measurements were made with a well-type NaI(Tl) scintillation counter connected to a single-channel analyser.

Extraction studies : Solutions containing 10 μg of silver was taken in a series of stoppered tubes and the acidity of all the solutions was adjusted in the range of 1–6 M with nitric acid. To these solutions, a substoichiometric amount (80% stoichiometry) ($0.93 \text{ E-}04 M$) sodium isopropyl xan-

thate solution (0.8 ml) was added. The silver complex formed was extracted with nitrobenzene (2 ml). The organic layer (1 ml) was separated into a counting tube. The extent of extraction was ascertained from the activity of the extract. The extraction behaviour of Ag : isopropyl xanthate was studied as a function of molarity of nitric acid against the activity isolated.

Reproducibility of substoichiometric isolation :

A series of solutions containing silver in the range 1–12 μg were prepared. Each solution was adjusted to 4.0 M with nitric acid. A constant amount ($0.93 \text{ E-}04 M$) of the sodium isopropyl xanthate solution (0.8 ml) was added. After equilibration for 5 min, the solutions were extracted with nitrobenzene (2 ml). The organic phase (1 ml) was separated and its activity was measured and plotted as a function of volume of tracer silver.

Calibration : Solutions containing inactive silver in the range 4–12 μg were prepared from the stock solution. A constant amount of the tracer (4 μg) was added. The solutions were made upto 4.0 M with respect to nitric acid. Equal but substoichiometric amount of sodium isopropyl xanthate corresponding to 80% stoichiometric amount was added and equilibrated for 5 min. The contents were then extracted with nitrobenzene (2 ml). The activity (a) of 1 ml of the organic phase containing the silver complex was determined. Under similar such conditions the activity isolated from the tracer (a_s) without the inactive silver was measured. The values of the ratios (a_s/a) were studied as a function of the added inactive silver to obtain calibration.

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